

THE PARENTAL DISCIPLINARY PRACTICES AS PERCEIVED BY THE GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179572>

ABSTRACT

Parental discipline refers to making a child obey certain rules and parameters and is important in shaping a child's well-being. This study investigates the parental disciplinary practices as perceived by the Grade 7 students in one of the schools in Qatar for the school year 2023-2024. It specifically explores the prevalence of disciplinary practices such as physical, verbal, and consequential discipline. Utilizing a quantitative descriptive research design, a self-made survey questionnaire was developed and validated for the study. A total of 172 respondents participated and were chosen using a simple random sampling method. The findings reveal that verbal discipline is the most commonly utilized practice among the respondents' parents. Therefore, it is recommended that parents employ subtle use of communication and conflict-resolving skills, which develops the idea that children can be more open to their parents.

Keywords: *disciplinary practices, parental discipline, verbal discipline, consequential discipline, disciplining practices, discipline*

INTRODUCTION

Around the world, discipline is oftentimes instilled within the household through various means by parents to their children when misconduct occurs, this is to impart comprehension about the consequences of their actions, responsibility, self-control, and

such; however, the intention of disciplining the children may not align with the means the parents partake in doing, and in turn, would not successfully entail the desired outcome of learning (Raising Children Network, 2023).

Promoting parental nurturance and responsiveness contribute to a child's emotional well-being, social competence, and overall development; when parents provide consistent and age-appropriate discipline, children are more likely to develop self-control, empathy, and pro-social behaviors, as they foster trust and security in the parent-child relationship, essential for healthy development. (Cherry, 2022). In addition, words of affirmation were the common form of love language, and Generation Z always felt loved whenever positive words and phrases were spoken to them. This provides evidence to the study as parental discipline also caters to the use of communication in employing the discipline of the parents to their children (Baranao et. al., 2022).

On the other hand, negative forms of parental disciplines, such as psychological violence appear as threats, yelling, harsh speech (Hartiani et. al., 2017), or corporal punishment which is common and deemed as a norm in the Philippines (Senate of the Philippines, 2010), can have detrimental effects on a child's well-being; studies have found that harsh parenting is a risk factor for children's aggressive and violent behaviors wherein they have found that children who experience authoritarian or neglectful parenting may be more prone to conduct problems, academic difficulties, and emotional disturbance (Kwok & Fang, 2022)

Parental discipline is undeniably a fundamental aspect of a student's upbringing, influencing their behavior, attitudes, and overall development. Parents are responsible for disciplining their children by teaching them what is right and wrong, how to follow laws and regulations, and how to behave properly (Hambala et al, 2023).

This study sought to enhance parent-student relationships by exploring diverse disciplinary approaches; it focused on Grade 7 students, and aimed to uncover alternative more effective disciplinary strategies, addressing concerns about harsh disciplinary practices prevalent despite existing discourse; the researchers selected the Grade 7 students as their respondents because they wanted to know whether the disciplinary practices were still being used or if they had changed as children entered the stage of adolescence and they are more likely to adjust and adapt to their environment.

The research questions are formulated to narrow down the main inquiry to extract more specific responses. The questions revolved around the parental disciplinary practices as perceived by the grade 7 students.

This study could be a great source of information to the body of knowledge through the analysis of the respondents' perceived disciplinary practices experienced, what they are, and what they do to them, which can function as the foundation for the development of methods and strategies for discipline that can foster empathy and awareness between the two. This mutual understanding can root for a deepened healthy relationship that has proper boundaries and support. The findings and results of the study can be the

foundational basis for parents and future parents in terms of disciplining their children, and what the children can do to strengthen their role in the family, all of which aim at improving the household.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the parental disciplinary practices as perceived by the Grade 7 Students in one of the schools in Qatar for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age; and
 - 1.2. sex;

2. What are the respondents' perceived parental disciplinary practices in terms of:
 - 2.1. physical discipline;
 - 2.2. verbal discipline; and
 - 2.3. consequential discipline?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research to fully illustrate how Grade 7 students are disciplined by their parents. Descriptive research attempts to gain a deeper understanding and meaning of single words or concepts. (Sirisilla, 2023) Additionally, descriptive research is also stated as a type of research used by researchers to describe a particular population or situation in an accurate and in-depth manner, relying only on empirical observations. Moreover, one of the more common ways to conduct descriptive research is through the employment of surveys that are used to gather the necessary information to make deeper analysis and commentary regarding the gathered information on the findings. Furthermore, the method does not ascertain the cause-and-effect relationship of the findings. In addition, the current research engaged the quantitative approach in obtaining the data through the circulated survey questionnaires.

The goal of the study is to classify and determine different parental practices as to how they are viewed by the Grade 7 level students, and how often they are implemented. It focuses on three main categories of parental disciplinary practices namely Physical, Verbal, and Consequential Disciplines.

The research questions were formulated from different literature focusing on the three main classifications of parental disciplinary practices. These questions were then validated by experts before they were released for the Grade 7 students to answer.

Research Locus and Sample

This study was conducted in one of the schools in Doha, Qatar. A total of one hundred sixty-five (165) grade 7 students, eighty-two (82) males, and eighty-three (83) females, were selected as the participants of this study. The researchers made use of a simple random sampling method in choosing the participants. This is defined as taking a small, random portion of the entire population to represent the entire data set, where each member has an equal probability of being chosen (Hayes, 2023).

Data Collection and Ethical Consideration

Research ethics were strictly employed throughout the study's completion. A request letter was sent to the office of the Vice-Principal of the department. Upon getting approval, this was forwarded to the Principal's office as prescribed in the communication protocol. In identifying the respondents of the study, another letter was sent to the office of the Registrar aiming to get the official list of students per class. An orientation was conducted for the class advisers and students through the research teacher. The goal of the orientation was for them to be fully aware of the data-gathering procedures. On the week of floating questionnaires, a letter as part of the questionnaire was addressed to each respondent and gave them enough time to finish the Google Form for paperless communication and ease of the process. The data was then carefully tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. Plagiarism checks were conducted to ensure the authenticity of the study.

Data Analysis

This study used data collected from a self-made validated questionnaire. The perceived parental practices were tallied using the weighted mean. It was verbally interpreted based on their value: 1.00-1.75 is Not Practiced, 1.76-2.50 is Slightly Practiced, 2.51-3.25 is Moderately Practiced, and 3.26-4.00 Highly practiced.

RESULTS

The study delves into Grade 7 students' experienced disciplinary practices from their parents. It aims to express the ways that are commonly used by parents to discipline and bring into line their children. Central to this exploration is the central question, "What are the parental disciplinary practices as perceived by the Grade 7 Students?" Additionally, this study is also focused on the specific question, "What are the respondents' perceived parental disciplinary practices in terms of physical discipline; verbal discipline; and consequential discipline?" A parent's ultimate goal in disciplining their children is to make sure they develop themselves from their mistakes, but it is important to note what kind of discipline they instill in their children.

1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Table 1
The Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
12	113	68.48%
13	49	29.70%
14-15	3	1.82%
Total	165	100%

Out of the sample size of 172 respondents, only 165 or 95.93% of the respondents answered. It is also notable that out of the 165 students, 113, or 68.48% are twelve years of age, 49, or 29.70% are thirteen years old, and 3, or 1.82% are aged 14-15 years old.

Table 2
The Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	82	49.70%
Female	83	50.30%
Total	165	100%

Table 2 exhibits the profile of the students according to their sex. It shows that 165 respondents were included in this research. Out of one hundred sixty-five (165) respondents, there are 82 or 49.70% with the sex of male, and 83 or 50.30% with sex of female.

When the respondents' age is taken into mind, the connection between parenting techniques, parenting styles, and behavioral issues in youth becomes even more complex. The developmental transition from childhood to adolescence is marked by changes in the body, mind, and social interactions. (Zlomke et. al., 2013) The adolescent

stage age group has a recommended form of disciplinary practice much different than that of the previous age groups (Vanbuskirk, 2022).

2. Perceived Parental Disciplinary Practices

Table 3
Respondents' Experiences with Parental Physical Discipline

	WM	VI	Rank
1. I am being disciplined by my parents through spanking by physical means.	2.24	Slightly Practiced	1
2. I experience being tapped by objects as a disciplinary measure from my parents.	2.21	Slightly Practiced	2
3. I experience being nudged when being disciplined at home.	2.19	Slightly Practiced	3
4. I experience taste cues implemented by my parents, (e.g. hot sauce, soap) as a form of discipline, to help me remember lessons when I need guidance.	1.28	Not Practiced	5
5. I am held to uncomfortable positions by my parents to instill my accountability as a form of discipline.	1.61	Not Practiced	4
Overall Weighted Mean	1.91	Slightly Practiced	

Legend: WM - Weighted Mean; VI - Verbal Interpretation

- 3.26-4.00 Highly Practiced
- 2.51-3.25 Moderately Practiced
- 1.76-2.50 Slightly Practiced
- 1-1.75 Not Practiced

Table 3 presents the perceived physical parental disciplinary practices enforced on the respondents. The statements that ranked first, second, and third which are slightly practiced talked about the respondents being disciplined in terms of spanking, nudging, and tapping with the use of an object with the weighted means 2.24, 2.21, and 2.19

respectively. On the other hand, statements 4 and 5 which refer to being fed various taste cues and being put in uncomfortable positions have a weighted mean of 1.28 and 1.61 which are verbally interpreted as not practiced.

The overall weighted mean of Table 3, which discussed the physical disciplinary practices used by parents of the respondents is 1.91, which is verbally interpreted as slightly practiced. The statement with the highest frequency tackles discipline in terms of spanking. This revealed that although rarely done to the respondents, they have encountered physical discipline through means of hitting and it also confirms that the physical discipline technique continues to apply to the respondents, despite growing adolescents and now in high school, as it is thought to make children more obedient and to encourage improved conduct.

This is in line with a study, as the data presented regarding the use of physical disciplinary practices suggests a promising decline in the use of corporal punishment, signaling a shift towards more constructive and compassionate approaches to discipline, rather than a rough use of force in discipline (Frchette & Romano, 2017)

Table 4
Respondents' Experiences with Parental Verbal Discipline

	WM	VI	Rank
1. I am spoken to in a firm manner when being disciplined at home.	3.37	Highly Practiced	2
2. I clearly acknowledge my faults when being disciplined at home through dialogue with my parents.	3.39	Highly Practiced	1
3. I converse with my parents about my shortcomings causing me to reflect and come up with better solutions for them.	2.87	Moderately Practiced	4
4. I am given the opportunity to express my perspective when being disciplined at home.	2.87	Moderately Practiced	4
5. I am being treated by my parents with courtesy in conversations when being disciplined at home.	3.11	Moderately Practiced	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.13	Moderately Practiced	

Legend: WM - Weighted Mean; VI - Verbal Interpretation

3.26-4.00 Highly Practiced

2.51-3.25 Moderately Practiced

1.76-2.50 Slightly Practiced

1-1.75 Not Practiced

Table 4 reveals the verbal practices imposed by parents to discipline onto the respondents. The highest ranked statements which refer to being acknowledged by the respondents' faults and being firmly spoken to when disciplined yielded a weighted mean of 3.39 and 3.37, which are verbally interpreted as highly practiced. This is followed by being treated with courtesy when conversing which has a weighted mean of 3.11, which is verbally interpreted as moderately practiced. The statements regarding speaking about the respondents' shortcomings for reflection and being allowed to express both had a weighted mean of 2.87, which is *moderately* practiced.

The overall weighted mean of Table 4, which discussed the parental verbal disciplinary practices implemented towards the respondents, is 3.13 verbally interpreted as moderately practiced. The statement that involves parents using dialogue to help their children acknowledge their faults has the highest weighted mean which showed that it is always occurring for the respondents, it stated that the parents use a stern communication style to allow them to own up to their wrongdoings. Furthermore, this data showed that, despite being conscious of their flaws, the respondents are frank and able to communicate with their parents. The respondents' behavior can be changed through communication given that they've developed effective communication skills that they can employ to resolve conflicts, create connections with their parents and other individuals, and instill trust.

This is parallel to a study, which emphasized the importance of parental empathy and understanding in fostering compliance and positive behavior in children. This underscores the significance of fostering open dialogue and mutual respect within parent-child relationships, ultimately contributing to healthier dynamics and positive developmental outcomes for children (Grusec et. al., 2017)

Table 5
Respondents' Experiences with Parental Consequential Discipline

	WM	VI	Rank
1. I am allowed to face natural consequences (unavoidable outcomes from actions or events.) as a form of discipline based on my misbehavior.	2.95	Moderately Practiced	2
2. I am assured of the logical outcomes (natural outcomes resulting in a child's actions with others) actions if I don't comply with the rules and expectations.	3.07	Moderately Practiced	1
3. I experience my privileges being revoked as a consequence when being disciplined at home.	2.67	Moderately Practiced	4
4. I am given limitations to my forms of recreation and leisure like "screen time" as a form of discipline.	2.92	Moderately Practiced	3
5. I am restricted from joining other activities when being disciplined at home.	2.17	Slightly Practiced	5
Overall Weighted Mean	2.76	Moderately Practiced	

Legend: WM - Weighted Mean; VI - Verbal Interpretation

- 3.26-4.00 Highly Practiced
- 2.51-3.25 Moderately Practiced
- 1.76-2.50 Slightly Practiced
- 1-1.75 Not Practiced

Table 5 shows the consequential disciplinary practices used by the parents towards the respondents. The statement that tackles respondents being assured of the logical outcomes of possible noncompliance with household rules and expectations had a weighted mean of 3.07, followed by the statement in which the respondents are allowed to face natural consequences as discipline for their misconduct, with a weighted mean of 2.95, the statement which involves limiting the respondents' forms of recreation and screen time as a disciplinary tactic has a weighted mean of 2.92. The next statement

involving being deprived of privileges as a consequence has a weighted mean of 2.67. Lastly, the statement which talks about restrictions from joining other activities as a form of discipline has a weighted mean of 2.17. All the statements are verbally interpreted as moderately practiced.

The overall weighted mean of Table 5, has a calculated weighted mean of 2.76, these disciplinary practices are moderately practiced within the context of the study. With a weighted mean of 3.07, the statement about assurance of logical outcomes in case of non-compliance with household rules and expectations shows that the disciplinary method prioritizes open communication regarding the consequences of acts. The possible consequences may happen if the responses disobey the guidelines and expectations that their parents have already explained referred to as the logical outcomes. All of these findings pointed to the respondent's awareness of the possible consequences of their actions alone, which makes them attentive to their conduct while maintaining a consistent approach to behavior guidance when combined with clear communication.

This is in line with a study, which states that all activities are choices and hence result in outcomes. The table aligns with this principle by indicating that respondents will face the consequences of their own actions, which underscores the importance of personal accountability and the understanding that individual decisions have corresponding effects, emphasizing the need for thoughtful consideration and responsibility in behavior (Krakoff, 2020).

DISCUSSION

This study highlights how students' perceived parental disciplinary practices are moderately practiced, wherein the respondents are given the platform to acknowledge their faults or misbehaved acts when being disciplined at home; through dialogue, resolution of conflict can be easily solved.

It focuses on the perception of Grade 7 students in one of the schools in Qatar for the school year 2023–2024, attempting to examine the parents' practice of discipline. The questions in this study were answered using a self-made questionnaire which was also validated by experts, the questions were formed through various research on the commonly used forms of discipline, which are regarding the physical, verbal, and consequential disciplinary methods. Based on the findings of the study, the null hypothesis, *Parental disciplinary practices, and their forms were not practiced as perceived by the respondents* was rejected.

The respondents faced a variety of disciplinary methods in their household, all of which posed an impact on their daily lives. The main objective of this study was to uncover the disciplinary practices of their parents which were perceived by the respondents. By examining their experiences with the various disciplines, this research aimed to provide

a comprehensive understanding of the common profound strategies and approaches of the parents that contribute to the development of a healthy bonded relationship between the parent and the child, and the constant growth of the child through it. Parental discipline is mostly done through the use of Verbal Discipline, which is moderately practiced. It is predicated on giving a platform to acknowledge the respondents' faults or misbehaved acts when being disciplined at home; through dialogue, resolution of conflict can be easily solved.

Conclusions

The findings based on the statistical analysis of data led to the following conclusions:

1. The grade 7 respondents of the study provided valuable information based on their demographic profile as to age and sex which are crucial in understanding the perceived disciplinary practices of their parents towards them.
2. The most commonly employed disciplinary practice is verbal discipline which recognizes the respondents' misbehaviors, and through dialogue, it enables them to reflect and express their perspectives crucial to navigating challenges and conflicts constructively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In adherence to ethical standards, this study obtained informed consent from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation and right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity was rigorously maintained to safeguard respondents' privacy, and measures were taken to protect their well-being throughout the research process. There is no conflict of interest, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and bias was eliminated in the interpretation of findings, ensuring the results are solely used for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The researchers wish to express their gratitude and appreciation to all those who supported and guided them throughout the study, especially to the following:

Dr. Alexander S. Acosta, the Principal of the Philippine School Doha, for letting the researchers experience crafting a research paper.

Dr. Lorina S. Villanueva, the QAAD Vice-Principal, and **Dr. Caridad A. Canete**, the Junior High School Vice-Principal, for following the researchers to conduct their study in the Junior High School level;

Mr. Elmeron L. Barañao, the Research Adviser, for offering guidance and advice on matters regarding the study and for also assisting the researchers throughout the study.

Dr. Julieann Real, Dr. Nida H. Garcia, QAAD Members, the institutional research board, for critiquing, giving valuable insights needed for the refinement of the study.

The Grade 7 Students, the participants of this study, for their participation and for dedicating their time and hardworking effort to conduct the study.

Mr. and Mrs. Espiritu, Mr. and Mrs. Amoncio, Mr. and Mrs. Ruiz, Mr. and Mrs. Desierto, Mr. and Mrs. Doyola, and Mr. and Mrs. Gloria for supporting and motivating the researchers to complete the paper.

Ram Anthony A. Medalle and Paul Mario O. Sadsad for their constant support and encouragement in fulfilling the completion of the paper.

And lastly, **the Almighty God** for giving the researchers strength and motivation all throughout the study.

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